

Figure 9 — Structural spurious correlation: genuine Preisach-MHTAR
Price-level correlation exceeds i.i.d. RW null (KS test); return-level correlation ≈ 0

Price-level R^2 distribution
MHTAR vs. i.i.d. random walk null

Return-level R^2 distribution
(≈ 0 : innovations genuinely independent)

